

ISic1524

I.Sicily inscription 1524

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15528

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐτελεύτησεν Πορ
2. φύριος μηνὶ Μαρτίῳ
3. ταῖς ἡέντε ἐτῶν κ καὶ
4. μῆνός Μνησθῆ σου ὁ θεὸς καὶ
5. ὁ Χριστὸς καὶ τὸ ἅγιος
6. πνεῦμα Εὐμυρωδὶς
7. ἀθάνατος α □ ω

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1896

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645024

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.28
Orsi, P. 1896. Gli scavi a S. Giovanni a Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 10: 1-59. At 59

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